

Fertilizer phosphorus requirement of rice and wheat grown on sodic soils

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Sodic soils, formed under the influence of sodium carbonate, are widespread on the Indo-gangetic plains of India. Sodic soils are nonproductive because of the high levels of exchangeable sodium, which causes the poor soil physical properties and high pH. Efforts are made to bring sodic soils under cultivation by the use of amendments and the adoption of appropriate agronomic practices. Because rice has high tolerance for excess sodium and has reclamation effect, it is recommended for cultivation on sodic soils during the initial years of reclamation.

Our knowledge of the dynamics of phosphorus (P), a major plant nutrient, during reclamation is limited; therefore this study was initiated to examine the P status of sodic soils and to identify the P fertilizer needs of rice and wheat grown on such soils.

A survey of the P status of barren sodic soils from many sites showed high amounts (15 to 68 ppm) of Olsen's extractable-P in the surface layer (0-15 cm), which decreased with depth and were highly correlated with the soils' electrical conductivity (EC).

To define the optimum P fertilizer needs of rice and wheat grown in rotation, a replicated field experiment involving P application to neither crop,

Effect of phosphorus application on the yield of rice and wheat grown in sodic soil. Karnal, India.

Treatment ^a	Yield (t/ha)							
	Rice				Wheat			
	1976	1977	1978	1979	1976	1977	1978	1979
R ₀ W ₀	5.0	6.2	5.4	5.4	2.2	0.9	2.9	3.0
R ₀ W ₅₀	5.1	6.0	5.2	5.9	3.1	1.1	2.7	3.2
R ₅₀ W ₅₀	4.8	6.0	5.4	6.0	3.6	0.9	3.0	3.4
C.D. at P = 0.05	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns

^aR = rice, W = wheat. Subscripts refer to P applications in kg/ha.

Effect of P application on the P status of an alkali soil under rice - wheat crop rotation. R = rice, W = wheat.

to rice, to wheat, and to both crops was initiated in 1976 on a barren, previously uncultivated sodic soil (pH = 10.3; EC = 4.6 mmho/cm, and Olsen P = 23 ppm). A rapid initial decrease in extractable-P after gypsum application and rice growth was due to the leaching of P to

lower layers and also to its immobilization to less-soluble Ca-P compounds (see table and figure).

For rice and wheat grown in newly reclaimed sodic soils, application of P fertilizer can be withheld for the first 3-4 years. ■

Effect of azolla manuring without incorporation

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Earlier trials conducted at PES revealed the possibility of saving 25 kg N/ha when a layer of azolla is incorporated into the soil before planting. The second crop raised in double-cropped wetlands can best use azolla. But because the farmer plants the second crop shortly

after harvest of the first, the growing and incorporation of azolla before planting are not possible. Therefore, growing azolla after planting was tried. Because the farmers do not practice line planting, incorporation of azolla is difficult. Therefore, azolla as dual crop was tried without incorporation.

In a trial conducted during the thaladi season of 1979, azolla was introduced as seed material at 3 t/ha a week after planting. Different levels of nitrogen — 0, 25, 50, 75, and 100 kg/ha — were tried with and without azolla but with

Grain yield of ADT31 in plots with and without azolla. Tamil Nadu, India.

Treatment (kg/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)
N 0	3.0
N 0 + azolla	3.2
N 25	3.5
N 25 + azolla	3.6
N 50	3.9
N 50 + azolla	4.0
N 75	4.4
N 75 + azolla	4.5
N 100	4.8
N 100 + azolla	5.0
C.D. (P = 0.05%)	0.4

the same level — 50 kg/ha — of P₂O₅ and K₂O. The test variety was ADT3. The azolla covered the plots on the 13th day after introduction and was left without being incorporated till harvest. The wet weight of azolla was recorded 20 days after planting. The values ranged from 0.98 to 1.27 kg/m² (mean of 10 values

was 1.09 kg/m²).

The maximum yield increase by growing azolla as a dual crop without incorporation was 0.2 t/ha; for N application at 25 kg/ha, the yield increase ranged between 0.4 and 0.5 t/ha (see table). It was earlier observed at this station that when azolla at 3 t/ha was introduced as

seed material a week after planting and incorporated on the 13th day — when it has completely covered the area — it gave a yield comparable to that from 25 kg inorganic nitrogen/ha [IRRN 5(3) (Jun 1980): 21]. Therefore, growing azolla without incorporating it did not add any appreciable N input to the crop. ■

Environment and its influence

Effectiveness of supplied nitrogen at the primordial panicle stage on rice plant characteristics and yields

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Ting and associates pointed out in 1959 that formed spikelets and rachis branches of rice usually degenerate during cultivation. Degeneration in the field can be 25.8% for spikelets, 3.8% for the primary branches, and 42.7% for the secondary branches. Matsushima reports that 40-50% of the spikelets degenerate and pointed out in 1957 and 1970 that the reduction division stage, which occurs about 11-13 days before flowering, is most sensitive to degeneration.

We investigated the application of nitrogen to indica rice varieties at the primordial panicle stage to develop improved cultural practices that would increase yields.

The application of nitrogen at the differentiation stage of primary branching increased the number of effective panicles, the number of filled grains per panicle, and the grain yield of the early-season variety Zhen-Zhu-Ai more than its application at the formation stage of pistils and stamens, at the formation stage of the pollen mother cell (PMC), or at heading (Table 1). Although nitrogen application at the differentiation stage or at the formation stage of pistils and stamens increases the number of panicles and grains, application at the formation stage of PMC or at the heading stage can increase the number of grains per panicle and grain weight. So, if nitrogen is applied only once, early

Table 1. Effect of nitrogen application at different panicle stages on grain yield using the early-season variety Zhen-Zhu-Ai. Guanezhou, China.

Stage when nitrogen was applied	Effective panicles (no./40 plant hills)	Panicles (no./hill)	Filled grains		1,000-gram wt (g)	Dry grain yield of 40 plant hills (kg)
			No./panicle	%		
Differentiation of primary-branch primordia	494	12.3	118.9	95.5	25.1	0.800
Formation of pistils and stamens	482	12.1	104.6	94.7	25.1	0.775
Formation of pollen mother cell	418	10.4	105.4	93.6	25.8	0.775
Heading	379	9.5	109.8	94.8	25.5	0.700
No treatment	367	9.2	103.5	92.4	25.4	0.700

application is better.

Field experiments in 1975-1976 with the early-season varieties Nanking-11 and Zhai-Ye-Qing showed that nitrogen applied at the differentiation stage of the first branch primordial (i.e., neck-node initiation) stage and of the primary primordial branch gave 150-225 kg higher grain yield/ha than heavy nitrogen application at the vegetative stage. With the late-season varieties Bao-Tai-Ai and Bao-Gou grain-yield increases

were sometimes 166-787.5 kg/ha.

But nitrogen application only increases yields under the following conditions. 1) Short-statured, nonlodging plants with erect leaves are used. 2) Leaves turn yellowish green at the end of the tillering stage, indicating that carbohydrate metabolism has gained over nitrogen metabolism. The carbohydrates stored in the leaf sheath and stem contribute to panicle growth during the primordial panicle stage, thus filling

Table 2. Distribution of ¹⁴C and ¹²P among the different parts of primordial panicle.

Plant parts	³² P (cpm/g dry wt)		¹⁴ C (cpm/g dry wt)	
	Control ^a	Treated ^b	Control ^a	Treated ^b
<i>Differentiation stage</i>				
<i>First bract primordia</i>				
Upper	2,880	2,020	—	—
Middle	2,800	2,890	—	—
Lower	2,560	1,980	—	—
<i>Secondary branch primordia</i>				
Upper	2,040	2,080	—	—
Middle	1,940	2,730	—	—
Lower	1,850	2,720	—	—
<i>Formation stage</i>				
<i>Stamens and pistils</i>				
Upper	3,810	4,450	1,045	1,120
Middle	3,920	5,280	740	1,080
Lower	3,880	4,140	720	1,060

^aNo nitrogen. ^b750 kg urea solution (1%)/ha, at the differentiation stage of primordial panicle.